

Composite coatings with embedded fibers and particiles for multiple impact protection

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Leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades

- Wind turbines operate under various weather conditions such as heavy rain and wind, with required lifetimes of around 20-30 years
- With increasing blade length, tip rotation speeds reach velocities as high as 100 m/s
- Blades impacting rain drops and other particles at such speeds lead to erosion of the surface with current coating solutions

→ **Develop new erosion resistant coatings**

Role in the Duraledge project

Some of several focus areas

Initial knowledge for choice of filler particles to test

"Products"

New improved coatings

- Multilayers?
- Particle combinations?
- Material systems?
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[1] Doagou-Rad S and Mishnaevsky L 2020 Rain erosion of wind turbine blades: computational analysis of parameters controlling the surface degradation *Meccanica* **55** 725–43

[2] Mishnaevsky Jr. L, Fæster S, Mikkelsen J. P, Kusano Y and Bech J I 2020 Micromechanisms of leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades: X-ray tomography analysis and computational studies *Wind Energy* **23** 547–62

[3] Doagou-Rad S, Mishnaevsky L and Bech J I 2020 Leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades: Multiaxial critical plane fatigue model of coating degradation under random liquid impacts *Wind Energy* 1–15

[4] Jespersen K M, Monastreyckis G and Mishnaevsky L 2020 On the potential of particle engineered anti-erosion coatings for leading edge protection of wind turbine blades: Computational studies *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **942**

Purpose of current work

Goal: Develop new erosion resistant coatings

→ **Use modelling to reduce the number of cases to be tested experimentally, and reveal new possible improvement combinations one had not imagined**

What makes coatings erosion resistant?

Hypothesis 1: Scattering of stress waves can improve the erosion resistance

Hypothesis 2: A network of fibers can improve the damping properties and thus the erosion resistance

Modelling of water droplet impact

- Water droplet impact has been modelled e.g. by SPH impacting a solid

Simplification of impact for particle comparison

- Assumed that a small unit cell will be subject to approximately homogeneous impact load

Considered particles

- Unit cells generated by Digimat software

4 vol% discs

1 vol% fibers

4 vol% fibers

8 vol% fibers

Hypothesis 1

Scattering of stress waves

Studying first stress wave after impact

- Impacted 0.005mm over 0.001ms (5 m/s)
- Linear elastic materials
- Symmetry boundary conditions
- First stress wave compared for
 - Pure PU
 - 4 vol% discs
 - 4 vol% curves fibers
 - 8 vol% curved fibers

Scattering of the first stress wave

- For 4 vol% particles, the stress waves travels quite similar for discs and fibers, but stresses are locally near fibers transferred further into the depth
- For 8 vol% fibers, the stress waves are additionally scattered and faster reaches the bottom of the unit cell

Effect of fiber volume fraction on stress waves

4 vol% fibers

(video)

8 vol% fibers

(video)

Hypothesis 2

Damping induced by fibers

“Bouncing” of unit cell to simulate damping

(video)

Average displacement of impacted surface

Inspired by vibrations theory the damping of the system can be estimated by how quickly the unit cell stops moving

Effect of fiber volume percentage on “damping”

- Pure PU bounces with higher average amplitude and lower frequency than all fiber cases
- Not much difference between 1 vol% and 4 vol%
- For 8 vol% significantly different behavior is observed

→ Look into more details of the mechanisms of 8 vol% case

High stresses in matrix for 8 vol% fibers

(Video)

High stresses in matrix for 8 vol% fibers

Viscoelastic damping of the unit cell

Considering larger volume and periodic boundary conditions could possibly fix this issue

Conclusions and outlook

On the potential of particles for erosion protection

- Presence of particles scatters the stresses – more pronounced for higher vol%
- Presence of fibers dissipates more viscous energy - more pronounced for higher vol%
- Additional viscous dissipated energy in high stressed regions could in turn also lead to crack initiation points if weak interfaces
- **However**, a highly interconnected network of pulp could potentially work as crack progression stoppers
 - Further work includes combined experimental trials and expanded models

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Extra

Duraledge project

- A total of six work packages, where the first three are:

WP1: Understanding of the leading edge erosion

- E.g. establish test and characterization methods to understand the behavior of existing coatings

WP2: Multiscale computational modelling and numerical simulation of leading edge erosion

- Develop tools for numerical testing and optimization leading edge protection solutions

WP3: Optimized protective solutions with engineered coatings

- Develop new erosion resistant coating solutions

- Highly interconnected

Highest stresses in bouncing unit cell (8 vol% fibers)

[4] Jespersen K M, Monastyreckis G and Mishnaevsky L 2020 On the potential of particle engineered anti-erosion coatings for leading edge protection of wind turbine blades: Computational studies *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **942**

Signals fitted to free vibration theory

(a) Pure PU

(a) 8% fibers

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Signals fitted to free vibration theory (energy)

(a) Pure PU

(a) 8% Kevlar

[4] Jespersen K M, Monastyreckis G and Mishnaevsky L 2020 On the potential of particle engineered anti-erosion coatings for leading edge protection of wind turbine blades: Computational studies *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **942**

Material properties

Table 1: Elastic material properties and density

	Young's modulus [MPa]	Poisson's ratio [-]	Density [g/mm ³]
Polyurethane	300	0.475	0.00118
Kevlar	70500	0.36	0.00144
Nepheline Syenite	150000	0.2	0.0026

Effect of particles on stress waves

Pure PU

(video)

4 vol% discs

(video)

4 vol% fibers

(video)